

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES, RISK MANAGEMENT CAPABILITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN THE SERVICE SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Purpose – This research aims to examine the mediating role of Risk Management Capability in the relationship between financial management practices and organizational performance.

Design/methodology/approach – In the Baltistan Region of Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan, data from 100 participants from 15 Banking Sector organizations were examined. Regression analysis was used to evaluate the validity and dimensionality of the research variables.

Findings – According to the findings, financial management practices are essential for predicting organizational performance. The connection between organizational performance and financial management practices is strengthened by risk management capability.

Research limitations/implications – In the context of Baltistan, the data were restricted to a cross-sectional design, which would make it less suitable for extrapolation across Pakistan. Furthermore, the sample size is comparatively smaller, although this has no negative impact on the results.

Originality/value – Research on the function of risk management capability and financial management practices is currently lacking in the context of Pakistan. This research serves as a comprehensive effort to explore how Risk Management Capability affects the link between Financial Management Practices and Organizational Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Attracting students, forming collaborations, and maintaining long-term financial stability are all made more difficult by the service sector's inability to effectively communicate distinctive value propositions and take use of possible synergies (Mlambo et al., 2017). Many service industries face

severe resource constraints, particularly in developing countries such as South Africa (Mohamed, 2020). Partnerships can provide access to more funding, knowledge, and facilities that individual institutions might not be able to obtain on their own (Brooks et al., 2012). Organizations can provide their clients

better and more complete services by pooling resources through strategic collaboration. Organizations face both possibilities and challenges as a result of the rapid evolution of technology (Gopalan, 2016). Effective financial resource management is essential to a company's ability to compete (Khokhlova G et al., 2019). Other researchers equate the financial condition with "the status of capital during its circulation and the capability of the entity to self-develop at a given time" (Savitskaya G V 2016). Even though there are many different ways to define the financial condition, assessing how well financial resources are being used to determine whether their quantity needs to be adjusted is an essential part of the study. An organization with sound financial standing has an edge when it comes to luring in investments, obtaining loans, and selecting suppliers and clients (Kretova et al., 2017).

Effective financial management is essential for the global services industry's operational success. In the service sector, it has become increasingly clear in recent years that effective financial management is crucial. This is because the service sector is facing a number of serious issues, such as limited resources, rising costs, and the need to provide high-quality services to a varied audience (Mosadeghrad., 2015). Organizations are constantly urged to create, implement, and rapidly adapt their financial management tactics in order to improve financial performance and capabilities and reduce risk (Erambo et al., 2016). A stronger commitment to and execution of financial management practices leads to improved business outcomes (Coleman and Cohn, 2017). Ineffective financial decision-making is the result of inadequate financial management (Dwangu and Mahlangu, 2021; Kiyabo and Isaga, 2019; William, 2018).

Several studies have shown that a company's operational efficiencies are enhanced by the interpersonal and interfirm relationships that information technology and online information capabilities promote (Johnson et al., 2007; Vaidyanathan & Devaraj, 2008). Relation-specific resources and knowledge-sharing practices are unique, socially, and operationally complicated (Johnson et al., 2007), and they contribute directly to a competitive advantage. According to Wade and

Hulland (2004), a company's information resources facilitate the development of competitive advantages through spanning and outside-in capabilities. Outside-in capabilities relate to the development of externally-oriented business intelligence and connections, with an emphasis on understanding competitive landscapes, meeting customer demands, and forecasting market trends. Spanning capabilities involve aligning information both internally and externally, closing the traditional knowledge gaps that exist between companies, between departments, and across the supply chain.

Especially in unpredictable and complicated contexts, Risk Management Capability (RMC) has become an essential component of organizational performance and resilience. The capacity to successfully manage risks becomes a fundamental strategic skill as companies encounter more dynamic risk environments (Mikes & Kaplan, 2015). This literature review examines important topics, theoretical foundations, and empirical research related to RMC in order to give a complete picture of its contribution to organizational success. Organizational performance is improved by financial management practices through their impact on effectiveness and efficiency (Erambo, 2017). However, despite the evidence pointing to a beneficial link between financial management practices and organizational outcomes, the mechanisms by which these practices influence performance are surprisingly underexplored (Akpan et al., 2022). The majority of research on SMEs' financial management practices is focused on developed countries such as the UK (McMahon, 2001), the US (McMahon and Holmes, 1991), Italy (Sensini, 2020), Canada (Bahri et al., 2017), Germany (Henschel, 2006), Spain (Chalmers et al., 2020), and the Netherlands (Maes et al., 2005). Yet, there are only a handful of studies on the financial management practices of SMEs in West Africa (Abor, 2007; Adegbe and Alawode, 2020). Financial management practices are essential to the effective operation of SMEs (Mwangi and Biruda, 2015; Nketiah, 2018; Zaridis et al., 2021). The literature emphasizes the important impact of financial management practices on an organization's performance and competitiveness (Adegboye & Iweriebor, 2018; Brijlal et al., 2017; Nthenge & Ringera, 2017). Financial management practices are

regarded as a crucial resource and a source of competitive advantage (Mwashi & Miroga, 2018). The current study adds to the literature on the subject in several significant ways. It provides suggestions for resolving issues related to organizational performance in emerging countries like Pakistan. A research inquiry was then conducted to analyze how financial management practices affect organizational performance. The relationship

between Financial Management Practices, Risk Management Capability, and Organizational Performance in Pakistan has not yet been studied. We then used system management theory (Khan et al., 2022; Samuel and Jacobsen 1997; Yoon and Kuchinke, 2005) and resource-based view (RBV) theory (Khan et al., 2020; Onjewu et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021).

Figure 1: Research Model

Literature review:

Financial Management Practices:

According to Coleman and Cole (2017), financial management is essential to the management of financial resources. According to Vohra and Dhillon (2014) and Waweru and Hgugi (2014), financial management is critical to the future of exemplary firms. Ahmed and Mwangi define financial management practices as a collection of established routines designed to handle financial reporting, budgeting, and other tasks associated with corporate funds. According to Dwangu and Mahlangu (2021), effective financial management practices are essential for overseeing financial resources and making informed financial choices. Numerous writers describe asset management, capital budget management, and working capital management as components of financial management procedures (Alles et al., 2021). According to Louw et al. (2022), effective working capital management is crucial to an organization's financial stability and a major contributor to its profitability and success. An essential aspect of financial management, capital budgeting is crucial for determining capital investment choices (Ross et al., 2016). Quality asset

data from multiple sources is integrated in asset management to support decision-making (Abdirad and Dossick, 2020). Organizations' profitability and financial stability are aided by financial management practices (Deakins et al., 2018). Effective financial management practices ensure that there is enough cash flow generation (Deakins et al., 2018; Salazar et al., 2013).

Risk Management Capability:

Managing Risk Capability is frequently described as an organization's capacity to systematically and successfully identify, evaluate, address, and monitor risks (Manab, Kassim, & Hussin, 2010). According to ISO 31000 (2018), RMC comprises principles, frameworks, and processes that align risk practices with strategic goals. It includes structural, processual, and cultural aspects that promote proactive and integrated risk management (IRM) methods (Frigo & Anderson, 2011). According to Aven and Renn (2009), RMC combines participatory decision-making with specialized knowledge as a technical and social skill. Numerous researchers have suggested multidimensional RMC models. For example, Teece (2007) emphasizes the importance of sensing, seizing,

and transforming in managing uncertainties while including risk management as a component of dynamic capabilities. Similarly, Andersen and Schröder (2010) define RMC as a combination of operational procedures, risk culture, and governance frameworks. Numerous studies confirm the beneficial link between robust RMC and business performance. For example, Meidell and Kaarbøe (2017) discovered that companies with developed risk management skills had improved strategic flexibility and decision-making speed.

Additionally, Razali and Tahir (2011) found that RMC plays a significant role in attaining a competitive edge through better resource allocation, decreased losses, and increased stakeholder trust.

Organizational Performance:

Organizational performance is a multidimensional and complicated concept (Ateke & Akani, 2018; Singh et al., 2016; Wood & Ogbonnaya, 2018). Organizational performance is defined as the degree to which an organization meets its goals (Nitzl et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2008). Numerous writers support this viewpoint, proposing that a company's ability to develop strategies that fit the complexities and dynamic elements of a shifting environment defines its performance (Rehman et al., 2019; Shea et al., 2012). Similarly, many scholars believe that organizational performance is an important measure of the achievement of specific organizational aims and objectives (Laaksonen & Peltoniemi, 2018). According to Richard et al. (2009), organizational performance can be evaluated objectively through financial performance indicators or subjectively through non-financial metrics to assess success in achieving organizational aims and objectives. The integration of financial and non-financial indicators is supported by the literature, however (Dryer and Reeves, 1995; Harris and Mongiello, 2001). This study examined the financial, capital market, organizational, and human resource variables connected to organizational performance.

H1: Financial Management Practices has a significant positive effect on Organizational Performance.

H2: Financial Management Practices has a significant positive effect on Risk Management Capability.

H3: Risk Management Capability has a significant positive effect on Organizational Performance.

H4: Risk Management Capability mediates the relationship between Financial Management Practices and Organizational Performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Data was gathered from various full-time and part-time employees in Pakistan's Baltistan G.B. Banking sector. Participants for data collection were chosen using convenience sampling techniques. In addition to hard copies, data was collected online through WhatsApp, Facebook, and email. A covert letter accompanied the questionnaires and explained the study's purpose to the participants. It further informed participants that their responses to the survey are treated with anonymity and confidentiality. The only use for their answers is for academic reasons. Out of 150 questionnaires sent, 118 were returned, and 100 were considered valuable. The response rate for usable data was 66.66%. Table 1 provides information on the sample's characteristics and distribution. According to the results, 67% of the total participants were women and 33% were men. Furthermore, 32% of the participants were single, and 68% were married. The majority of the respondents (90%) were part-time employees, while the remaining 10% were full-time workers. Furthermore, 30 percent of the participants were between the ages of 18 and 25. Conversely, 40% of the respondents were in the 26 to 30 age range, while 30% were between the ages of 41 and 60. Among all respondents, 60% worked in management, 10% in maintenance, 10% in technical services, and 20% in clerical positions. Sixty percent of the respondents had 0 to 5 years of work experience, eight percent had 6 to 10 years, twelve percent had 11 to 20 years, and twenty percent had 21 to 30 years. No respondent had over thirty years of professional experience.

Measures

Financial management practices were evaluated using asset management (Kelly and Hardy, 2018), capital budget management (Balarabe, 2020), and working capital management (Mazlan and Choong, 2018). The reliability rating for the fourteen items was 0.782. The study on Risk Management Capability,

which served as the mediating variable (Power, M ,2007), produced three results. The alpha reliability for Risk Management Capability was 0.855. Organizational performance was assessed using financial outcomes (Rowe and Morrow, 1999), organizational outcomes (Chenhall and Langfield-Smith, 2007), human resource outcomes (Dryer and

Reeves, 1995), and capital market outcomes (Richard et al., 2009). The alpha reliability for organizational performance was 0.877. A 5-point Likert scale was used to evaluate all variables in the study, with 1 indicating strong disagreement and 5 indicating strong agreement.

Table 1: Characteristics of Sample Distribution

Table 1: Distribution and Characteristics of Sample

Variable	Categories	No	(%)
Gender	Male	33	33
	Female	67	67
	Total	100	100
Marital Status	Signal	32	32
	Married	68	68
	Total	100	100
Age	18-25	30	30
	26-40	40	40
	41-60	30	30
	Over 60	0	0
	Total	100	100
Work status	Full time	90	90
	Part time	10	10
	Total	100	100
Position	Management	60	60
	Maintenance	10	10
	Technical Service	10	10
	Clerical	20	20
	Total	100	100
Experience	0-5	60	60
	6-10	8	8
	11-20	12	12
	21-30	20	20
	Over 30	0	0
	Total	100	100

Every item was scored using a Likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 meant "Strongly Disagree" and 5 meant "Strongly Agree." Organizational Performance 's Cronbach alpha reliability was (0.899).

Controlling element / Controller Variable

The study's control variables included age, gender, and sector, according to a prior Khan study conducted in 2022. The study utilized the following coding for variables: Age (1 = under 25 years, 2 = 26-30 years, 3 = 31-40 years, 4 = 41-50 years, 5 = 51-60

years, and 6 = over 60), gender (1 = male, 2 = female), and section (1 = public, 2 = private).

All study variables were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 represented strong disagreement and 5 represented strong agreement.

RESULTS

To examine the variation in Organizational Performance based on the demographic factor analyzed in this study, one-way ANOVA was employed. According to the One-Way ANOVA

results (see table 2), there were no substantial differences in the mean Organizational Performance score between various Genders, Ages, or Sectors.

Table 2: One-way ANOVA

Sources of variation	OP	
	F statistics	p-value
Gender	.310	.798
Age	1.999	.155
Sector	.877	.478

OP= Organizational Performance

Statistical Tools: Means, standard deviation, correlations, Reliabilities and multiple regression analysis also using SPSS 22 version.

Results

Table 3: Means, Standard deviation, correlation and Reliabilities

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	
FMP	3.73	0.74	(0.782)			
RMC	3.86	0.99	0.568**	(0.855)		
OP	3.55	0.99	0.688**	0.899**	(0.877)	

FMP= Financial Management Practices, **RMC=** Risk Management Capability, **OP=** Organizational Performance

The data in Table 3 shows that Financial Management Practices are strongly positively correlated with Organizational Performance (0.688, $p = .000$), thus completely supporting hypothesis 1. Additionally, there is a positive correlation between Financial Management Practices and Risk Management Capability (0.568, $p = .000$), which supports hypothesis 2. Finally, Risk Management Capability is positively correlated with Organizational Performance (0.899 $p = .000$), which supports hypotheses 3 and 4, respectively.

Regression Analysis:

The Baron and Kenny (1986) mediation criteria were used in the current investigation. Regression analysis was employed to assess the variable's main and mediating effects. The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table 4. The results show that Financial Management Practices have a very positive and important effect on Organizational Performance ($\beta = 0.899$, $R^2 = 0.289$, $p = .000$), which supports Hypothesis 1. Hypothesis 2 has been accepted in light of the clearly advantageous and significant effect of Financial Management Practices on Risk Management Capability ($\beta = 0.818$, $R^2 = 0.223$, $p = .000$). The results also indicate that Risk Management Capability has a significant and positive effect on Organizational Performance ($\beta = 0.911$, $R^2 = 0.955$, $p = .000$). Therefore, we accept hypothesis 3.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Predictor	Risk Management Capability			Organizational Performance		
	B	R ²	▲R ²	B	R ²	▲R ²
Direct effect						
FMP	0.818***	0.223	0.244***	0.899***	0.289	0.299***
OE				0.911***	0.955	0.961***

Indirect effect						
FMP X RMC				0.888***	0.866	0.877***

N = 100. FMP = Financial Management Practices, RMC = Risk Management Capability
 *p < .05. **= p < .01. ***= p < .001. ns = not significant

Based on the results of the mediating regression analysis presented in Table 3, Risk Management Capability mediates the relationship between Financial Management Practices and Organizational Performance ($\beta = 0.888$, $R^2 = 0.866$, $\Delta R^2 = 0.877$, $p = .000$). As a result, Hypothesis 4 is accepted.

Discussion and Managerial Implications:

The positive and significant effect of Financial Management Practices on Organizational Performance in the Baltistan banking sector, mediated by Risk Management Capability. The current study shows that Financial Management Practices are essential for Organizational performance, especially in the banking industry. To improve performance and gain a competitive advantage in the marketplace, Management and Administration should prioritize financial management.

Limitation and future research

The results of this study, conducted in Pakistan's G. B. Baltistan area's baking sector, may not apply to other contexts. Future studies might include more sectors from across the nation in order to produce and discover reliable results. Since the present study controlled for employee demographics such as age, gender, and sector, future studies may look at other demographic variables. This study's findings and conclusions are derived from the banking industry. Researchers comparing banking and tourism may conduct future studies.

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